

Studies in Salt Activation. Part I. Influence of Neutral Salts on the Enzyme Hydrolysis of Starch.

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Although it is well known that many enzyme reactions are accelerated or retarded by salts, the mechanism of the effect has not been studied in detail for any particular enzyme. A general theory concerning the effect of ions on the activity of enzymes has not yet been developed, because of the different mechanism of salt action in different cases. The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken with a view to throwing light on the nature of the salt action on the enzymic hydrolysis of starch in particular and other enzymic reactions in general.

The activating effect of neutral salts on the activity of pancreatic amylase under varied conditions has been thoroughly investigated by Sherman and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 2596; 1928, **50**, 2529, 2535, 2538) and Willstätter, Waldschmidt-Leitz and Hesse (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1923, **136**, 143).

Michaelis and Pechastein (*Biochem. Z.*, 1914, **59**, 77) have investigated the nature of salt activation of salivary amylase. They observed that the diastase is inactive in the complete absence of salts and it combines with all the salts to form double compounds, each of which having very characteristic properties, depending upon the anion of the salt. Each of these complex compounds has diastatic action but differs (a) through the affinity of the salt (or anion) for the diastase, (b) by the degree of their activity upon the starch (or the affinity of the complex salt-diastase compound for starch), and (c) by the acid dissociation constant and on the position of the isoelectric point and the H-ion of its optimum activity upon starch. The isoelectric point of all the salt complexes was found to be between 10^{-5} and 10^{-6} , and the optimum activity for PO_4 , AcO , SO_4 was pH 6.1 to 6.2; for Cl and Br , 6.7; and for NO_3 , 6.9.

Contrary to the observations of Michaelis and Pechastein, (*loc. cit.*) Myrbäck (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1926, **159**, 1) observed that salivary amylase is active even in absence of salts. The salt and one of its ions, com-

bined with the enzyme and the amylase-salt complex thus formed, was found to be more active only in its undissociated or isoelectric form. Combination with a salt altered the degree of dissociation of the enzyme, thus changing the proportion of the enzyme in the active form at any given pH.

There is, however, much controversy regarding the action of neutral salts on vegetable amylases. Some workers observed activation, viz., Eadie (*Biochem. J.*, 1926, 20, 1016), with barley malt amylase, at salt concentration of 1.62N; Patwardhan and Norris (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1928, 11A, 127) with cholam malt diastase; Narayanamurthy (*ibid.*, 1930, 13A, 63) with cholam malt amylase at 0.00016N-salt concentration; Sherman Caldwell and Cleaveland (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2406) with barley malt amylase at an unfavourable H-ion concentrations, and Lisbonne (*Soc. Biol.*, 1912, 72, 936) with electrolysed malt amylase; and some others noticed inactivation or no effect in presence of salts.

Fricke and Kaja (*Ber.*, 1925, 57, 310, 313) observed inactivation with electrolysed barley malt amylase; Narayanamurthy and Norris (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1928, 11A, 104) noted inactivation with electrolysed cholam malt diastase; Karmakar and Patwardhan (*ibid.*, 1930, 13A, 159) with wheat amylase observed no effect.

Some interesting observations on salt action have been made with potato amylase by Haen and Schweigart (*Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 143, 516) who separated an almost free and inactive amylase by dialysis and ultra-filtration which could be activated by salts and amino-acids. Very recently James and Cattle (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 1805) working with potato amylase observed that the enzyme responsible for the immediate breakdown of starch molecule to form 'dextrins' is capable of activation by potassium chloride, while another enzyme responsible for the production of sugar from the dextrin, produced by the first enzyme is incapable of such activation.

The foregoing observations by several workers point out the need for further systematic work on the subject. The contradictory results obtained by foregoing authors and several others are chiefly due to the fact that the pH of the reaction mixture was neither controlled nor observed. Even in those cases, where the pH had been controlled by the addition of buffers, the effect of these buffer salts on the activity of the enzyme, which sometimes depends on their concentrations, had not been thoroughly investigated. A systematic investigation of the problem with all the necessary experimental precautions seemed, therefore, the only means of reaching a satisfactory solution.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the enzyme.—Preparations of the amylase were obtained from sweet potato by the following three different methods, (i) by the alcohol precipitation from a direct aqueous extraction of the dried sweet potato meal as described by Venkata Giri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 339), (ii) by ordinary dialysis in collodion bags of the aqueous extract of the meal at -1 to $+1^{\circ}$ temperature in a cold room, (iii) by adsorption on alumina gel, elution, and dialysis, a method developed by Giri (*Biochem. Z.*, 1934, 275, 106) for the purification of the enzyme.

Methods of procedure.—The activity of the enzyme was measured as described in the previous communication. In experiments in which the reaction was to be carried in the presence of neutral salts, the latter were added from the stock solutions to the reaction mixture, the concentration of the neutral salt present in the total volume of reaction mixture (100 c.c.) is expressed as molar concentration.

The hydrogen-ion concentrations of the substrates were adjusted by sodium acetate and acetic acid buffer of a total concentration of $0.04M$ -acetate. For higher ranges of pH values, phosphate buffer was used. Soluble starch (Zulkowsky's) was used as substrate.

All the salts employed in the present investigation were of the highest grade of purity, either Merck's or Kahlbaum's guaranteed analytical reagents.

The degree of acceleration of the hydrolysis produced by the neutral salts is always expressed as percentage acceleration, (A) which is calculated from the formula

$$A = \frac{(y-x)}{x} 100$$

where x denotes the activity of the enzyme in absence of salt, y , the activity of the enzyme in presence of salts. In this way, the results of all the series were made quantitatively comparable.

The Influence of the Concentration of Acetic Acid-acetate Buffer of Varying H-ion Concentrations on the Hydrolysis of Starch.

Reaction mixture containing 100 c. c. of 1% starch and buffer of varying concentrations and pH were prepared. The H-ion concentrations of the substrates were adjusted by sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer of total concentration of $0.04M$, $0.08M$ and $0.12M$ -acetate. The temperature of the reaction mixture was 30° . The enzyme

solution was prepared by dialysis of the aqueous extract of the powder. 5 C. c. of the enzyme solution were used for each hydrolysis experiment. The results are presented in Table I. In the following table k denotes the activity and (A), the percentage acceleration.

TABLE I.

Buffer concentration (activity $k \times 10^3$).

p_H .	0.04M.	0.08M.	0.12M.
2.8	12.06	1.2	0
4.0	17.90	3.5	1.2
4.5	20.10	19.8	3.2
5.6	29.40	30.1	29.4
6.0	30.40	30.4	30.8
6.5	25.60	25.6	26.6

The figures indicate that at high concentrations of 0.08M and 0.12M and at p_H more acid to the optimum, the hydrolysis is very much depressed by the buffer. But at p_H 5.6 to 6.0, which is the optimum one for the enzyme, and on the alkaline side of the optimum p_H , the concentration of buffer has no influence on the enzymic hydrolysis of starch. Hence, to avoid the adverse effect of buffer salt, the hydrolysis experiments were always carried at low concentrations of buffer (0.04M). The H-ion concentrations of the substrates were always, therefore, adjusted to a total concentration of 0.04M-acetate.

Influence of Neutral Salts at Varying H-ion Concentrations on the Enzymic Hydrolysis of Starch.

The influence of neutral salts upon the activity of the amylase was studied at three different H-ion concentrations, viz., optimum p_H (6.0), acid side of optimum p_H (4.0), and alkaline side of optimum p_H (8.0), in presence of 0.1M concentration of the salts. In the case of sodium chloride, the activity of the amylase was studied in the presence of 0.1M and 0.5M concentrations of the salt at closely graded H-ion activities from p_H 2.7 to 8.0.

The reaction mixtures consisted of 2% starch, buffer of varying p_H present in a total concentration of 0.04M-acetate and salt, the total volume of the reaction mixture amounting to 100 c.c. including the quantity of the enzyme added. The enzyme preparation used for

these experiments was obtained by precipitation with alcohol from the aqueous extract of the powder. The hydrolysis was carried at 30°.

The results are presented in Tables II and III and graphically represented in Fig. 1. It will be seen from the results that sodium chloride in the region of p_H , 5.6 to 6.0 and sodium fluoride, sodium nitrate and sodium sulphate at p_H , 6.0 are without effect on the activity of the amylase. This region corresponds to the region of optimum p_H which has been previously established for the enzyme. On comparing the activity of the enzyme in presence of 0.1M sodium chloride and in its absence at p_H 2.7 to 4.6, the activity is greater in its presence, the percentage of acceleration increasing towards the more acid region. Thus, it can be seen from Table I, that the percentage of acceleration at p_H , 4.6 is 11.2 which increases with rise in the acidity and finally reaching a maximum acceleration of 84.4 at p_H 2.7. On increasing the concentration of sodium chloride to 0.5M, the acceleration is decreased.

FIG. 1

Influence of NaCl on the activity of amylase at different p_H .

1. Without salt. 2. With 0.1M-NaCl. 3. With 0.5M-NaCl

The activity of the amylase is unaffected with 0.1M-NaCl, but is considerably depressed with 0.5M-NaCl in the range of p_H , 6.5 to 8.0.

The influence of sodium fluoride, sodium nitrate and sodium sulphate was studied in the same way as that of sodium chloride but the

influence of these salts was measured only at p_H 4.0, 6.0 and 8.0. A similar acceleration was observed at p_H 4.0 in the presence of these salts, and at its optimal hydrogen-ion concentration the amylase was as active without as with the neutral salts. At p_H 8.0, however, the activity of the enzyme is not affected by the presence of the salts. Sodium sulphate, however, depresses the activity at p_H 8.0. It is probable that the depressing effects of these salts in the alkaline region may be pronounced when the concentration of the salts is increased.

Thus the amylase shows optimal action through a wide range of H-ion concentration in presence of neutral salts. The foregoing results point out the need for controlling the H-ion concentration of the reaction mixture when the effect of neutral salts on the activity of amylase is to be studied. Further, these observations explain the contradictory results obtained by several workers when studying the influence of neutral salts on the activity of vegetable amylases.

TABLE II.

Starch conc. = 2%. Amylase conc. = 0.01%. Salt conc. = 0.1M.

NaCl conc.	p_H .	Activity $k \times 10^4$		(A).
		with NaCl.	without NaCl.	
0.1M	2.7	47.2	25.6	84.4%
	3.4	48.1	27.2	76.9
	4.0	54.2	37.3	45.3
	4.6	57.6	51.8	11.2
	5.6	55.6	56.0	-0.7
	6.0	58.3	58.3	0
	6.5	41.0	41.0	0
	8.0	10.3	10.3	0
	2.7	40.4	25.6	58.0
	3.4	45.4	30.7	48.0
0.5M	4.0	15.9	37.3	23.0
	4.6	54.7	53.9	1.5
	5.6	57.7	57.7	0
	6.0	58.3	58.3	0
	6.5	38.5	41.0	-6.1
	8.0	7.1	10.6	-33

TABLE III.

Starch conc. = 2%. Amylase conc. = 0.01%. Salt conc. = 0.1M.

p_H .	$k \times 10^4$ without salt.	with NaF		Na ₂ SO ₄		NaNO ₃	
		$k \times 10^4$.	(A).	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).
4.0	36.0	54.6	51.7%	51.6	43.0%	48.9	35.8%
6.0	57.2	57.2	0	57.2	0	57.5	0.6
8.0	10.3	10.3	0	8.5	-17.4	10.2	0

Influence of Varying Concentrations of Neutral Salts on the Enzymic Hydrolysis of Starch.

The activity of the amylase in presence of varying concentrations (0.001M to 0.50M) of neutral salts and in their absence at p_H 4.0 was measured. The reaction mixtures consisted of 2% starch, acetic acid-acetate buffer of p_H 4.0 and salts of varying concentrations, the total volume of the reaction mixture amounting to 100 c.c. The results are presented in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Starch conc. = 2.0%. Amylase conc. = 0.01%. p_H = 4.

Salt conc.	NaF.		NaCl.		Na ₂ SO ₄ .		NaNO ₃ .	
	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).
0	36.0	...	36.6	...	36.6	...	36.6	...
0.001N	36.0	0	36.6	0	36.6	0	36.6	0
0.01	42.0	16.2%	42.3	15.6%	41.0	12.9%	39.7	8.5%
0.02	45.3	26.0	44.2	20.8	42.8	17.0	41.4	13.1
0.04	50.6	40.6	48.9	33.6	47.5	30.0	45.9	25.4
0.08	54.9	52.5	51.3	41.5	50.0	36.6	49.1	34.1
0.10	54.9	52.5	53.3	45.6	51.5	40.8	49.1	34.1
0.20	55.2	53.3	53.3	45.6	51.6	40.8	49.1	34.1

The figures in Table IV show that the activity of the amylase increases with the increase in the concentration of neutral salts, reaching a maximum at salt concentration of about 0.10-0.20M. On

comparing the maximum acceleration of activity attained in presence of each salt, it can be seen that the activity varies with different salts. The results are shown graphically in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the curve corresponding to each salt is approximately a rectangular hyperbola, suggesting according to Michaelis' theory, that the salt probably combines with the enzyme to give a more active enzyme-salt complex. These salts can be arranged as follows according to the decreasing magnitude of their effects on the activity of the amylase at p_H 4.0: $\text{NaF} < \text{NaCl} < \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 < \text{NaNO}_3$.

FIG. 2.

Influence of varying concentrations of salt on the activity of the amylase at p_H 4.0.

The Influence of Cation on the Acceleration of the Enzymic Hydrolysis of Starch.

Reaction mixtures containing 1 % starch and a total concentration of 0.1M of the salts in a total volume of 100 c.c. were prepared and

the activity determined. The hydrolysis was carried at p_H 6.0 and 4.0 at 30° and the results are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Neutral salt.	p_H .	$k \times 10^3$.	p_H .	$k \times 10^3$.
Control	4.0	19.0	6.0	34.1
LiCl	4.0	32.7	6.0	34.2
NaCl	4.0	34.8	6.0	35.0
KCl	4.0	32.2	6.0	36.0
CaCl ₂	4.0	34.0	6.0	36.1
BaCl ₂	4.0	34.2	6.0	36.4

The above results indicate that the cations of the salts investigated have no influence on the activity of the amylase. A similar observation was made by Norris (*Biochem. J.*, 1913, 7, 626) in the case of the hydrolysis of glycogen by pancreatic amylase. Cole (*J. Physiol.*, 1906, 30, 202) however, considered that the anion accelerated while cation depressed the action. If the latter were correct, the chlorides containing a bivalent cation should be less active than sodium or potassium chloride. The above results, as well as the observations of Norris (*loc. cit.*), suggest that such is not the case. The view that the anion is the more important factor in the acceleration of the hydrolysis of starch, is further strengthened by taking into account the relative accelerating power of fluoride, chloride, sulphate and nitrate.

Influence of Concentration of the Enzyme on the Accelerating Effect of NaCl.

A series of mixtures were made up each containing 2 per cent. starch and a concentration of sodium chloride ranging from 0 to 0.20M, the p_H of the substrate being adjusted to 4.0. When the concentration of the enzyme was 1 c.c., the aliquots were taken out at intervals of 20, 40 and 50 minutes, and at shorter intervals of 5, 10, and 15 minutes, when the concentration of the enzyme was increased to 2 and 4 c.c. The results are presented in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Conc. of NaCl.	Q u a n t i t y o f t h e e n z y m e.					
	1 C.c.		2 C.c.		4 C.c.	
	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).	$k \times 10^4$.	(A).	$k \times 10^4$.	(A)
0	18·8	...	36·8	...	74·5	...
0·001 M	18·8	0	36·8	0	74·6	0
0·002	20·9	11·2%	39·3	6·9%	27·7	4·3%
0·003	21·1	12·1	42·6	10·3	80·1	7·5
0·005	22·0	17·0	41·9	13·9	82·0	10·0
0·01	22·8	21·3	42·2	16·3	84·2	13·0
0·02	24·1	28·2	46·5	26·3	90·9	22·0
0·06	27·3	45·2	53·6	45·6	108·0	45·0
0·10	27·3	45·2	53·6	45·6	108·0	45·0
0·20	27·3	45·2	53·6	45·6	108·0	45·0

It can be seen from the results that the percentage of acceleration in presence of the salt, below a concentration of 0·02M varies inversely as the concentration of the enzyme. When the salt concentration exceeds 0·02M the accelerating action of the salt is independent of the enzyme concentration.

Influence of Substrate Concentration on the Accelerating Effect of NaCl.

A series of reaction mixtures containing 1, 2 and 3% of starch and of varying concentrations of NaCl were prepared, and the extent of hydrolysis was determined by allowing the hydrolysis to proceed at 30° for 15 minutes and estimating the maltose formed in the total volume (100 c.c.) of the reaction mixture. The p_H of the substrate was adjusted to 4·0. The results are shown in Table VII.

It can be seen from figures in Table VII that the accelerating effect of NaCl depends also on the concentration of starch, the higher the concentration of starch, the less is the acceleration produced by salt at the same salt concentrations.

TABLE VII.

Conc. of NaCl.	Starch concentration.					
	1 %.		2 %.		3 %.	
	Maltose.	(A).	Maltose.	(A).	Maltose.	(A).
0	135 mg.	...	171 mg.	...	198 mg.	...
0.02 M	162	20.0%	203	18.8%	230	18.2%
0.04	185	37.0	225	31.1	237	18.2
0.10	212	56.8	234	37.0	243	22.7
0.20	212	56.6	230	34.5	239	20.7

*Influence of the Purity of the Enzyme on the Accelerating
Effect of Salts.*

Since it might be expected that the salt acceleration, if a property of the enzyme itself and not of the impurity associated with it, would be characteristic and invariant, it was found necessary to investigate the phenomenon with more than one preparation of the enzyme subjected to various forms of treatment.

Enzyme preparation (A).—Prepared by alcohol precipitation from the aqueous extract of the dry powder. The concentration of the enzyme used was 0.01 %.

(B). Prepared by dialysis of the aqueous extract. 5 C.c. of the enzyme solution were used for each determination.

(C) Prepared by adsorption on alumina gel, elution and dialysis (Giri, *loc. cit.*).

The following is a brief description of the method adopted for the purification of the enzyme:—100 G. of the powder were extracted with 600 c.c. of water for 2 hours at the laboratory temperature and filtered. The filtrate was then centrifuged and dialysed in collodion bags in cold room at -1° to $+1^{\circ}$ for 4 days. 500 C.c. of the dialysed solution were mixed with 100 c.c. of acetic acid-acetate buffer ($M/5$) of p_H 3.7, and 10 c.c. of alumina gel (0.178 g. of Al_2O_3) and kept for 10 minutes with frequent shaking. It was then centrifuged and the adsorbate was eluted with 800 c.c. of $M/75$ -phosphate buffer at p_H 7.1 with frequent shaking for about 2 hours in a refrigerator and again centrifuged. The phosphate present in the centrifuge was removed by precipitation with magnesia mixture and the precipitate thus

formed was immediately filtered and the filtrate was neutralised with acetic acid. All these operations were carried at low temperature. The solution thus obtained was dialysed for 3 days in cold room and the enzyme solution thus purified was used for the following experiment.

TABLE VIII.

2% NaCl=0.1M.

p_H .	Precipitation A.			Precipitation B.			Precipitation C.		
	$k \times 10^4$.		(A).	$k \times 10^4$.		(A).	$k \times 10^4$.		(A).
	without salt.	with salt.		without salt.	with salt.		without salt.	with salt.	
4.0	36.1	53.0	46.8%	30.2	44.0	45.7%	39.0	56.5	45.0%
6.0	58.1	58.1	0	46.3	46.3	0	60.5	60.6	0
8.0	10.2	10.2	0	9.1	9.1	0	11.3	11.3	0

The results indicate that NaCl behaves in the same manner with all the enzyme preparations, showing thereby that the accelerating effect of the salt is essentially a property of the enzyme.

DISCUSSION.

The question whether neutral salts accelerate the hydrolysis of starch by the amylase, depends upon the H-ion concentration of the medium, and also upon the concentration of neutral salts. By suitably varying these two factors, acceleration, retardation, or no effect can be found. Thus the results in Tables II and III indicate that salts are capable of accelerating the velocity of hydrolysis of starch to an extent dependent upon the p_H of the medium. At p_H higher than the optimum (p_H 6.0) the reaction is retarded at high salt concentration, whilst below p_H 6.0 it is accelerated to an extent proportional to the acidity of the system.

H-ion determinations made by colorimetric method on starch solutions containing varying concentrations of neutral salts show that the reaction of the medium is not altered by the presence of salts in the concentrations employed. The p_H of the reaction mixture also remains unaltered during the course of hydrolysis. Hence the accelerating effect of neutral salts is not due to the above cause.

In order to explain the mechanism of salt acceleration the following possibilities may be considered:

Activation of the enzyme by the salts may be brought about either by

(1). (a) Altering its colloidal properties or (b) combining with the enzyme molecule to form compounds possessing different properties.

(2). By protection of the enzyme against heat inactivation or from inhibiting substances formed during the reaction.

Considering the possibility that salts may accelerate the hydrolysis of starch by altering the colloidal properties, a change in the degree of dispersion of the enzyme in presence of salts and as well as a change in the isoelectric point of the enzyme (Haehn and Harpuder, *Z. Biol.*, 1920, **71**, 302) are the factors to be taken into consideration in such studies. But in some cases the effect is so specific that no general theory can be offered.

It has been shown that anions are more concerned in the acceleration than cations. As to the reason for the variations produced by the anions, some change in the colloids, either of the starch or the enzyme or both, suggests itself. In the present investigation, it has been shown that the degree of accelerating effect of salts is dependent on the concentration of starch and of the enzyme. This suggests that the effect produced may be due to some changes in the enzyme and the substrate molecule. No definite evidence is so far available with regard to the nature of such a change. In the action of amylase on starch, both the substrate and the enzyme are colloids, and hence it is likely that the action of salts may not only be confined to the enzyme. In certain cases, however, where the substrate is not a colloidal solution, the influence of salts may be chiefly confined to the enzyme. Thus, the observations made by Cole (*J. Physiol.*, 1906, **30**, 281) that in the action of invertase, where the substrate is not a colloidal solution, salts have a powerful influence (in this case the hydrolysis is retarded by chloride), it is probable that the action of the salts is chiefly confined to the enzyme. It is, therefore, desirable to study separately the effect of salts on starch and enzyme from the point of view of adsorption and charge.

In this connection it may be of interest to mention the work of Biedermann (*Biochem. Z.*, 1923, **135**, 282; **137**, 35) whose results led to the following generalisations; of all the components of a system which apparently contains a diastatic enzyme, only the inorganic salt or its ions are able in association with oxygen to break down starch with the formation of sugar. The organic compounds are unable to effect this unless salts and oxygen are present. Thus the decomposition

tendency of the substrate in presence of neutral salts is another point to be considered in studies on salt activation.

Regarding the other possibilities it is likely that either the salts combine with the enzyme molecule to form compounds possessing different properties or that the salts accelerate the hydrolysis of starch by protecting the enzyme against inactivation or from inhibiting substance produced during the reaction. Further experiments are in progress to test the above hypothesis.

SUMMARY.

1. The effect of neutral salts like sodium fluoride, sodium chloride sodium sulphate and sodium nitrate on the hydrolysis of starch by the sweet potato amylase has been studied under varied conditions.

2. The salts accelerate the action of the amylase at p_H higher than 6.0, in presence of high salt concentration. Sodium chloride accelerates the activity at p_H below the optimum to an extent increasing with the acidity of the medium. At p_H 6.0, the activity of the enzyme is not affected by the presence of salts.

3. The accelerating effect of all the neutral salts at p_H 4.0 is found to increase with the increase in concentration of the salt, and the effect is lessened on further increase.

4. The salts may be arranged according to the decreasing magnitude of their effect on the activity of the amylase at p_H 4.0. Sodium fluoride $\angle$ sodium chloride $\angle$ sodium sulphate $\angle$ sodium nitrate.

5. The accelerating effect of sodium chloride on the enzymic hydrolysis of starch is influenced by the concentration of the enzyme and of the substrate.

6. The accelerating effect of salts is essentially a property of the enzyme.

7. Various possible theories to explain the salt activation have been indicated and discussed.

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